

Structures and semiotic systems

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Abstract

A model of interrelations between various types of mentation and semiotic systems is suggested. The relations of structures, forms, and signs in different mentation processes and their effect on semiotic systems are discussed. Major features of these systems are examined from the viewpoint of simulation of changes in physical objects and human environment. Most are multilateral and are clearly structures of various systems. Their organizing role in semiotic systemity are evinced through the analysis of architectural ensembles and separate architectural works (examples of Old Russian architecture and architecture of classicism).

Keywords: structures; semiotic systems; mental activity; signs; forms; information; architectural composition.

Based on the system of semiotic objects (Somov 2001, 2003) and semiotic studies of architecture, the author has attempted to examine the interrelations among structures, signs, and mental activity. This subject seems to be very important for the development of theoretical anthroposemiotics (Sebeok 1999).

Semiotic systems cannot be separated from the processes they exist in, which is reflected in general interrelations between sign and semiosis. Basic processes where the semiotic systems are formed, function, and evolve are behavior, activity, and, finally, communication and noesis developing in these processes (figure 1). The basic initial description, which makes it possible to unite these different processes and systems, is the regulation 'system-environment' model (Steinbuch 1965: 316–317).

The *regulation of 'system-environment' interrelations* (1–5, see figure 1) is divided into: (a) external, accompanied with the changes in physical characteristics (1) and including information and signs (2) (b) internal

Figure 1. *Basic elements of the formation, functioning, and development of semiotic systems. (I) Environment of physical characteristics (material objects); (II) Human environment; (III) Signs and sign systems regulating the environment I; (IV) Signs and sign systems regulating the environment II; (1) external regulation of environment; (2) informational processes of external regulation; (3) internal regulation (processes of a reflexive type); (4) regulation of changes in the environment of physical characteristics (material objects); (5) regulation of changes in the environment of physical characteristics (material objects); (6) activity; (7) mental activity; (8) processes associated with internal regulation; (9a) activity regulating material objects; (9b) proper communication; (9c) mixed activities; (10) models of mental activity; (11) structures; (12) forms; (13) structural mechanisms of mental activity; (14) free transformations of structures; (15a) models I; (15b) models II; (16) sign-synthesizing forms; (17) systems of a language type; (18) semiotic systems of various types of activity; (19) system-structural formations of a fragmentation type; (20) principles of organization of reality I and signs III; (21) principles of organization of signs IV and reality II; (22) general principle of structural organization (22a) and its manifestation in the processes of mental activity (22b). Lines denote basic interrelations*

regulation of a reflexive type (Steinbuch 1965: 316) (3). Regulation (1) corresponds to an environment with physical characteristics (Gibson 1986 [1979], 1982), while information-sign processes (2) correspond to an environment with sign characteristics or *Umwelt* (Uexküll 1982). The delimitation of these two environment interpretations is the object of semiotic analysis (Smith 2001). In connection with these processes, there are several basic types of regulation in human life: (a) regulation of changes in the environment of physical characteristics or material objects (I) with informational processes (4) involved, (b) regulation of changes in human environment (II) with their informational processes (5), and (c) regulation of internal status or processes of reflective type (3). In all types of regulation, the fundamental role belongs to signs and sign systems (in terms of the naturalistic approach by Peirce, who interprets signs as the fundamentals of life), as it is clearly formulated in numerous semiotic works (Sebeok 1999; Liszka 1996). Hence, different types of regulation and corresponding types of behavior and activity should possess fundamental meanings, basic codes and sign types, and *Umwelt* characteristics (III, IV).

Models of regulation should be complemented by the processes and motivations of denotation-noesis and orientation-evaluation (Morris 1971) and complicated in various directions, as it is done by their authors (Steinbuch 1965). In the frames of this article, we shall restrict ourselves to the most general distinctions.

Models of regulation characterize human behavior and sign functioning in general. However, in order to regard semiotic systems of a person and society, it is indispensable to introduce the category 'activity.' Some methodologists regard it as an initial category for system analysis (Yudin 1973; Shchedrovitskii 1995: 233–234).

Activity (6) is the continuation of environment changes. These changes occur with the help of the active transformations of objects. This corresponds to the term 'change management,' which defines activity in Project Management Theory. In the course of activity transformations, signs are involved in the processes of active selection of information, modelling of problem situations and their changes, creation of models of the future (goal), and its development in plans and projects; they participate in transformations of information, different operations, and communicative processes associated with activity. In particular, in order to create and implement a project of a new city (or dwelling region), sign forms of information are needed for projecting, discussion, advertising, apartment sale, construction, etc. The effect of activity processes on sign systems is especially apparent in large-scale projects of this kind. As a result, some authors point to the necessity of examining the signs 'inside activity'

(Shchedrovitskii 1995: 467, 543, 570). Specific sign formations appear in connection with objects and tasks of different activity types. A future building can be represented as a scheme of quarters, a draft of constructions, or a color picture of a building in the urban environment. These three types of sign systems are based on features, relations, and structures that are important for the resolution of different tasks: the creation of comfortable living conditions, solidity and processability of construction, and the formation of an artistic image. In connection with this, the systems of information representation and storing also differ. Project information can be represented and stored as schemes, graphs, tables, drafts, comments, and models; in some countries, they are regulated by special requirements of ‘project representation.’ This simple example illustrates how semiotic systems are formed in a definite activity system, based on natural codes, signs, and languages. Semiotic systems promote various activities and are organized in a total collective activity and in the general semiotic system of the latter.

Different activities are characterized by mental processes. In connection with this, it is necessary to identify their mental nucleus, or mental activity, according to Shchedrovitskii (1995: 281).

Mental activity (7), first and foremost, simulates situations; on this basis, goals, problems, and ways of their resolution are formulated (Pospelov et al. 1969). Despite the differences in activity types, analogous problem situations emerge when both material objects and human interrelations are changed. In both cases, an important role belongs to the processes of denotation-noesis and orientation-evaluation, motivations, differentiations, and specific meanings and functioning signs.

The processes associated with reflexive internal regulation (8) (Steinbuch 1965) generally denote various internal psychic processes: melancholic thoughts, contemplation, dreams, fantasies, and different autocommunications. These processes are interrelated with external processes of activity and behavior; but unlike them, they have no definite objects and situations, no definite goals and ways of their implementation, as they are relatively activity-free. Many signs apparently function and develop ‘in the processes of this type, being related to fundamental meanings’ (let us remember how many semiotic studies support directly or indirectly Freud’s Oneiromancy). However, it is difficult to discuss the effects of the signs of internal regulation processes and whether their simulation can be identified with models of external processes. We need unified systems of semiotic description of sign systems of external and internal psychic processes rather than empirical data. Within the frames of this paper, it is enough to fix the existence of this domain of the organization of sign systems as the object of semiotic modelling.

In order to reveal the causality of semiotic systems, it is important to pay attention to basic differences among activities, which determine sign differences. From this point of view, most important is to differentiate the activities into those regulating material objects (9a) and communications itself (9b).

The activity regulating material objects (9a) is represented by practical material transformations: usage of tools, engineering decisions and their implementation in processing, transport management, legal estate regulations, etc. In this range, the central and evolutionary initial position belongs to a creative activity, which started with the fabrication of Paleolithic stone tools. Creative activity enhanced the development of a specific way of modelling future objects: sign systems supporting the activities of this type. This point will be discussed below (12).

Communication (9b) manifests the contacts among persons, evolving from behavior. It can either be included in a more general collective activity or be independent of activity. Being involved in a more general activity, the communication (communicative activity) continues the basic one (Shchedrovitskii 1995: 484). Hence, communication basically can favor the changes in material objects or human environment (II). The latter are more important, because, in the changes of type II, the leading role belongs to special meanings, signs, and models. In this environment, mental activity is conducted due to, first of all, proper states and actions or emotional-motional acts, which either copy other persons or represent a response to their intentions and actions. This kind of simulation is necessary to effect other people and change their actions, relations, and psychic states, including their development. In the course of the identification of human states, intentions, and relations, symptoms and appellations (Bühler 1978 [1934]: 36–37) are merged with reactions-actions. A threat envisages clenched fists, while a smile causes a return smile. Hence, the development of code-symptoms is related to the development of code-appellations. The effect on other people is based on the formation of codes and signs expressing psychic states, which is most apparent in mimics and gesture. In this type of modelling, an important place is given to energies, forces, and other physical objects. However, like sensory objects, they are represented by signs. All signs of models II (IV) are included in psychic processes of orientation-evaluation, denotation-noesis, and proper communication. Models and signs of these processes are directly related to certain fundamental needs and corresponding intentions. First and foremost, they are in need in emotional compassion and search of the sense of life giving birth to self-affirmation. The representation of these intentions in information and signs has been discussed earlier (Somov 1985a, 2002).

Mixed activities (9c) join types 9a and 9b. Even the most ancient interrelations among people and animals gravitate to the activity in either the environment I (planned hunt) or II (domestication and friendship). During the evolution of human society, the management of changes in physical objects (via labor, distribution of resources, ownership, and other processes) intersects with human interrelations. As a result, the relations of the types $[II \subset I]$ and $[I \subset II]$ appear. More complicated activity types are formed, uniting types 9a and 9b with their models, signs, and semiotic systems. Mutual penetrations of activities and processes of internal regulation also occur (8), which are accompanied by the materialization of internal sign systems of a person ($8 \rightarrow 9$) and interiorization of sign systems of external processes ($9 \rightarrow 8$). Communications in artificially created material objects form independent domains of activity ($9b \rightarrow 9a$). Visual manifestations of these processes are table settings, fashion shows, and the design of interior and urban landscapes. In general, the synthesis of activities 9a and communication takes place with a clear manifestation of the basic differences and interrelations between the organization of material objects and communication signs. A typical example is the design of an apartment building where physical spaces and constructions are united with sign systems. To organize efficiently, the physical reality of an apartment building is to put in accordance different resources of public time, realtors' benefits, and saving of technological processes and materials. To organize a semiotic system is to create the conditions for the actualization of different types of information and synthesize various communicative situations, codes, and signs as a building (Somov 1990, 2002).

Different types of models of mental activity (10) are in the center of activities and formation of semiotic systems and represent certain system-structural constructions. The identity of various models is due to the fact that mental activities simulate fundamental relations of situations, especially those to be changed. These relations are generalized in simulation mechanisms and appear as structures.

Structures (11) are intrinsic to all processes and system constructions; they appear in interacting parties (Pi in 1972: 41) and become visualized at different levels of real world (Russell 2000: 225–226). A well-known statement 'Structures are not studied but constructed' (Martinet 1962: 4) refers to the ways of their description but does not abolish the objective character of structures. From this point of view, there is a certain problem of interactions between the structures of objects and those of their description, structures of physical reality, and mental structures. This is a component of a general scientific problem of ontological status of universals. We shall avoid discussing this problem, assuming that the structures of description and objects may not coincide.

As mental activity operates with fundamental interrelations of changeable situations, structures play an important part in different models of mental activity. A visit is planned by imagining a structure of route. Cutting firewood becomes efficient if the direction and strength of the cut is evaluated in the mind, considering the direction of wood fibers, and inverting moment of a cut log. These are the structures forming a general structure construction of a situation and prompting the actions as structure implementations. Even this simple example demonstrates that structures are organized in mental activity in a certain way. This happens in more general formations — organizations and totalities (Somov 2001) — and appears in a general organizing way of mental activity described by the word ‘form.’

Unlike high-abstract structures, *forms* (12) are more concrete. The emergence of this specificity is related to the processes of tool fabrication, the development of human hand, and progressing tactile way of modeling. Hence, some methodologists think that form and material appear only in human activity and are absent in nature (Shchedrovitskii 1995: 256, 280). The forms, which are seen in nature, are generated by system and structure formations, but only a human being can use the form to organize something.

They are the forms, which generate the processes usually called image mentality. Interrelations between images and forms are the most apparent in the experience of architects who search images by changing forms. These relations are explained by the fact that different indices and icons are created in forms due to the participation of structures. By linking structures, organizations, and totalities, the form makes it possible to simulate perceived objects not only as stable systems, but also as a multitude of denotations. These denotations are quite visual. A simple picture of housefront elements formed by element junctures, window framings, metal shaping strips, balcony and lodgia barriers, the location and size of openings, and a combination of different materials, is related objectively to the system of internal spaces, constructions, and building technologies. This is why this or that treatment of a housefront can designate each of these denotations. Figurally speaking, single structural features (representamens of these or those denotations) are incorporated in a form. The structure and size of spaces of architectural complexes are denoted via heterogeneities of volume, light-and-shade, and the dissection of housefronts. The denoted characteristics are: (1) general structure, corresponding to the term ‘tectonics,’ (2) real object size as related to humans, corresponding to the term ‘scale,’ (3) social and functional features of these objects, and other parameters indispensable for the simulation of urban environment (Somov 1986). These examples indicate that the form

contains signs and represents a way of mental activity due to the ability of single characteristics to denote real objects. The form thus has a dual nature: the way of organizing real objects (I) and their representation in various codes, signs, languages, and informational processes of models I (III). This makes it possible to understand that images are materialized as processes due to the incorporation of different codes and signs with following structure mechanisms. The very possibility of the incorporation of codes and signs into forms generates forms synthesizing codes and signs of a cultural origin. This idea will be discussed below (16).

The development of forms and forming processes is accompanied by level differentiation; first, a fundamental dimension is formed in accordance to the levels of integration from concrete to abstract. This dimension can be represented as the range: structures, frames, forms, and detailed models of constructed objects. The simulation in this direction is accompanied by the delimitation of totalities, factors, and systems, development of mechanisms of situation recognition, decision-making, etc. Structural mechanisms of mental activity are formed and fixed in the process of differentiation, within the frames of form of this and other dimensions.

Structural mechanisms of mental activity (13) are the most visual in case of intellect testing when it is necessary to find a missing element in a range of words, numeric values, or geometrical bodies. In these cases, the 'extraction' of structure takes place, being supported by its materialization via a continuation of the range, i.e., a resolution of the task. Different recognition processes also include these mechanisms. First, they identify some features using a given alphabet of structures and compare with standard structures of image classes. Complicated structural mechanisms are visualized in mind games, with the structures given in paradigmatics (game rules) and problem situations with different probability and variants of realization of given goal structures. The transformation of structures in planning and projecting works is somewhat different. In this case, the structures, which are necessary to organize municipal transport and pedestrian fluxes are separated and related to the structures of location of buildings and corresponding land plots. This helps to plan efficiently housing, net of streets, and location of official buildings.

These descriptions of structural mechanisms can be correlated with the descriptions of mechanisms of mental activity in psychology, first and foremost, those given by Piaget. For each constructive thought resolving a new task, his model envisages the participation of reflecting and correcting abstractions. The latter complements the first one with a system of correspondences that are indispensable for operations. These abstractions are regarded as 'sources of structural neoformations.' The elements,

transported from one level to another, are combined with either initial elements of this level or the elements that will be added there later (e.g., the rules of summation generate multiplication) (Piaget 1979: 56–57). In any case, it seems evident that various mechanisms of mental activity can be described as transformations of structures. In semiotic studies, it is important to represent these mechanisms not in the aspect of empirical cognition of mental processes, which is common in psychology, but to describe them as mechanisms of structural transformations (translations, materializations, decompositions of structures, etc.). In connection with this, several mechanisms can be distinguished: structural projection of a situation, comparison of structures, constancy of their isomorphism or difference, structural interactions in nodes followed by node materialization, decomposition of structures, translation to other relations, and other combinations. The simulation of architectural form demonstrates that these structural mechanisms are incorporated in the formation of signs and information (Barbyshev and Somov 1972, 1976; Somov 1990). This corresponds to some philosophical ideas regarding the information as the visualization of structural organization (Ursul 1971; Tyukhtin 1977). The structure of information appears directly in organizations and vital processes: biorhythms, symmetries, corresponding binary structures of sign systems, mechanisms of extrapolation of stochastic events, or elimination of ambiguity of choice in bifurcation points. The abstract character of structures determines their similarity in different mechanisms, processes, and systems forming the information as a whole and various processes of mental activity. This similarity explains the capacity to simulate mentally different situations, the similarities of ‘congenital mechanisms fixing similarities and differences,’ and constant character of these mechanisms in cultures and languages (Quine 1973: 19).

A special role in the development of semiotic systems belongs to the mechanisms that differ from the resolution of mental activity problems and conditionally can be called free mechanisms.

Free transformations of structures (14) are implemented in vital processes separated from practice and noesis; this corresponds to the idea of ‘the game of mentation cognitive capacities’ in Kant’s aesthetics. These mechanisms are described in theoretical informational studies of perception of music primarily as ‘the regularity of statistical expectation.’ These studies represent the extrapolation of structures of perceived fragments to future fragments with the stochastic distribution of events (Moles 1966). Analogous mechanisms are present in adventures and some games, including human relationships.

Structural transformations cannot be separated from signs because of their natural origin. As signs are relations, these relations contain

structures: in a sign itself (icons), in relations between objects and their representamens (indices), in mutual relations of signs, and their interrelations with designates (symbols). Structures and signs are interrelated not only in human mental activity, but in the phenomena of life in general. This continues the central naturalistic idea of sign theory by Peirce mentioned by contemporary semiotic scientists: ‘... Peirce claimed that every sign particles of a particular formal structure, which, though it appears in its most striking and sophisticated form in human language, is in fact suffused throughout the natural order’ (Liszka 1996: 15). Signs belong to the organic world and form the basis of life (Sebeok 1999; Sharov 1999). At the same time, as it has already been said, structures are regarded in a wider aspect as intrinsic to all realities and migrating from one reality to another. As a result, signs are usually not perceived by people. On the contrary, structures are transformed into designations, clearly represented in mind and easily identified in mentation and images as typological schemes, numeric ranges, mirror symmetries, structures of rhythm, lines, centers, and element identifications by various characteristics. These structures appear directly in gait, dance, and sportive games, as they can be and are the denotations and representamens of signs.

The similarity of structures does not annul their participation in mental activity processes, first, due to the differences between models I and II.

Models I (15a) are based on structures and relations of material objects: causal connections, determinations by certain facts, systems implementing certain processes, resource-minimizing relationships, etc. (Somov 1990). The signs used to simulate the situations of type I possess the capacity to denote the changes and structures of these situations (III).

Models II (15b) are involved in the recognition of life situations with the participation of humans. They are caused by the need of influencing another person, revealing his intentions, or changing relationships in a group of people. Fundamental situations of this type appear in logical informational systems, such as ‘agents — actions — objects,’ and result in the emergence of multiple assertions and their sign representations. At the same time, there are many states, motivations, and emotions that are hidden from structural simulation and its implementation in logical mentation and verbalization. They are incarnated in symptoms, appellations, and emotional-effector accompaniment of these signs. This channel allows one to penetrate the psychic reality of other people. This is why it is not reasonable to separate the emotional type of mental activity from the structuring of situations when analyzing human contacts. In general, significant factors in the development of models II are symptoms and appellations united with symbol systems, emotive interpretants of these signs,

and their basic representamens forming personal image. By linking the designates of symptoms and appellations in a structural way (using symbols and metalanguages), we can advance hypotheses and create models of the psychic world of other people. This simulation is vitally important and thus is organized in specific semiotic systems based on the abilities and habits of imitation, aesthetical perception, and emotional compassion. The specifics of models II help to understand clearly that semiotic systems of communication have another direction, as compared to practical material activity (I). They reproduce and form mainly emotional relations and spiritual contacts.

Hence, models I is initially envisaged for the extraction of structures in signs, while the models II primarily delimits signs with emotive meanings. Models I initially has a denotative-noetic direction related to the possibility of changing the structure of situations. Models II has, first and foremost, the direction towards orientation-evaluation and motivation, which is related to the changes in evaluations and actions. As the modelling of type I is more directly related to 'fundamental meanings' and different intentions, it is closely connected to internal processes of a reflective type.

While models I can be represented in a more definite and concrete way as form (12), the synthesis of models I and II in their more concrete manifestations appears in the forms synthesizing many signs.

Sign-synthesizing form (16) develops from a usual form, which simulates type I situations. The way of modelling, called 'form' and based on the combination of different structures, totalities, and organizations, is extrapolated in the combinations of many codes and signs. This generates the problems of interrelations and differences between structure and form, especially when studying complicated artistic semiotic systems, as it has been analyzed in detail in the semiotics of literature (Levi-Strauss 1970: 139–140; Prieto 1975: 15–28). But there are more visual examples of their interrelations: architectural forms. They contain signs, which are related to different code types, meanings, and concepts of culture (icons representing humans, indices of presence of otherworldly forces, or symbols generated by religious semiotic systems). Even simple historical architectural connotations generate significant art images of architectural objects. Atriums and porticoes address the forms of antiquity, the elements of dome architecture, arcades, and developed rectangular portals combined with rusticated stone represent the culture of Renaissance, while simplified Doric columns refer to the empire style. These and many other signs not only form the designates or language meanings, but relate them to the 'reality called semantics of possible worlds.' The incarnation of these forms proceeds in image-perceptions and image-representations, in

particular, those of buildings, streets, squares, and whole cities. Sign-synthesizing forms become the basis for the formation and development of human mentality within a definite culture and form the imaginative world of a human being.

As forms synthesize various signs, they also synthesize the structures of sign systems, organizations, and totalities of signs. This is why the role of structural organization is so important in painting, the formation of urban landscapes, clothing, jewelry, and all other objects addressed to visual perception. These objects contain the ornaments incorporated in form and organizing the levels of signs, representamens, and asemantic signals (Somov 1975, 1985b, 2005, in press).

The role of structures in the functioning of signs is especially evident in architectural formation. Structures are ways of connection, principles of separate systems construction — the characteristics included in certain processes. Such an interpretation of the concept ‘system’ corresponds to its general scientific definitions in the systemology by G. J. Klir (1985) and others. During architectural formation, the integration of various systems and their structures is appreciable. Evident manifestations of the composition and decomposition of structures in architectural form and in the formation of signs can be illustrated with characteristic examples of construction of architectural ensembles. Structural analysis of various architectural ensembles, cities, and individual architectural works carried out in the research of the author allows us to show 1) some set of structures of certain systems, and 2) some steady structures with their internal, actual structural properties (Barbyshev and Somov 1990; Somov 1990). In various mechanisms of structural integration in architectural formation, their fundamental properties as connections in space-time, and ways of organizing various relations are revealed. In particular, topological structures, numbers, symmetries (mirror symmetry, the module, metric recurrences), the common interval of changes (proportions), numerical expressions of proportions (the golden section, characteristic ratios of the absolute sizes of elements), connections of proportions and recurrences of elements (geometrical similarity) are of concern to them. Some such means were traditionally considered in the theory and various analyses of architectural composition.

In the functioning of semiotic systems in architecture, structures are directly connected to codes that the author earlier aspired to prove (Somov 2006, in press). The interrelations of structures and codes are revealed in visual perception. It is clearly an effective means of an architectural composition (Somov 1986, 2002). These means represent types of structural organizations of sign groups, relations, distinctions, and identities of visual different elements (representamens of signs by Peirce). Examples of

these groups of elements and relations are presented in figures 2–20. These structures in representamens are the bases of codes and promote realization of signs and certain ‘pieces’ of the information. In particular, the uniform module allows for the identification elements. The proportional structure enables the perception of a group of elements. It, as if, connects elements. Uniform linear constructions form connections of elements in space and are the basis of reading as integrity. The line connects elements, placing them in a single line. Characteristic organizing signs of these lines are included in codes of intentional character, in identification of culture objects, many vital situations and environmental objects.

Fundamental codes are realized based on some fundamental ways of organization. It is revealed in fundamental compositional means. The perception of danger or uncertainty is promoted by sharp inclinations, slants, dynamic planning directions, heavy hanging masses. The perception of the quiet environment is promoted by symmetric constructions, balance of mass, smooth flows of forms and lines, uniform transitions of the sizes from one architectural element to another. Information about the natural size of objects is better perceived through the creation of partitions, separate elements and their groups, elements allocated by certain features. Distances between buildings and other objects in space are coded by the structures of partitions of volumes (their distinctions as neutral and actively dismembered, vertically and horizontal, walled and glazed, largely dismembered and finely dismembered, etc.) With the help of these rather advanced composite means of a partition of surfaces, the effective information about spatial ratios of objects and about the spatial organization of large architectural complexes is achieved (Somov 1986). This is explained by the fact that the structures of change of a spatial interval are connected with the fundamental codes of the perception of space-time (Somjen 1972; Somov 2006, in press). For the maintenance of this type of information, the structures of identification codes connected with iconic signs are also included. Various antropomorphic features (structural attributes) promote the perusal of human figures, faces, and hands (Somov 2001, 2006). In particular, secrets of scale, figurativeness, and emotional meanings are revealed.

The role of structural mechanisms and forms in mental processes and their models helps us to better understand the functions, differences, and specificity of systems of language type (this term does not obligate us to restrict them to the models and terms of linguistics).

Language type systems (17) are formed in a unity and relationship with the development of mental activity. The efficiency of these systems is maintained by the processes uniting three types of signs: the indices, icons, and symbols of Peirce. This idea proved to be true when three types

Figure 2. Country wooden palace of Tsar Alexey Mikhaylovitch in Kolomenskoe near Moscow (1667–1681). Drawings of the palace were made under the order of empress Ekaterina II in 1780. The plan of the second floor. The mansions: 1 – Tsar, 2 – Tsarevitch, 3 – Tsarina, 4 – Princesses

of signs were revealed in the systems of linguistic language (Jakobson 1965). This can be extrapolated successfully to other systems. Images obtain the character of symbols and are completed by symbols, partly turning into hieroglyphs of a written language. In painting, the combination of represented situations and objects with mythological systems via linguistic metalanguages becomes the way of formation of whole art cultures. The combination of different sign types must not shadow a special role of linguistic language for mental activity and its importance for the development of other sign systems. 'Unmotivated character of linguistic sign' (Saussure 1959) favors mentation due to the possibility of the free combination of signs separated from denotations and the generation of designated combination (Martynov 1966). The possibilities of structural modelling of a situation, the creation of non-existing designates, and their structural combination become enlarged. A so-called 'concept mentation' is formed. The organization of designates following the principle of packing in large sign blocks appears. These tools make it possible to fix situations better, including their causal relations and mutual effect; the possibility of forming stable models of situations appears. In particular, in the case of simulation of social relations or the human psychic world, a developed (causal and structural) explanation of acts, motives, goals, and emotional relations is formed. It is important that linguistic tools of modelling are combined with form and corresponding types of mental activity.

Figure 2. (*Continued*)

Structures of material systems and processes: parts of a palace and their quantitative relations according to quantity of processes (summits, presentations, ceremonies, feasts, etc.), connections of family members (in particular, princesses live separately and under supervision far away from courtiers sights). *Structures of semantic relations in elements of material space* of the complex: quantitative relations of palace parts according to regal hierarchy (Tsar – Tsarina – Tsarevitch – Princesses); the size of each mansion designates its importance. *Structures of elements of perceptive space:* spaces of mansion form rhythms (from small spaces of entrance elements to large halls). Placement of mansion walls at a sharp angle to each other creates a variety of spaces of ensemble. This structure is also a basis of a code of traditional architectural systems of ancient Russian ensembles and palace complexes. Directions of the basic axes of palace mansions in old Russian architecture were made under corners to each other that was caused by a complex relief and disclosing into landscapes. This characteristic has turned during its evolution into an index of Russian architectural traditions. *Structures of changes of visual views:* placement of mansions comparatively to each other and the different heights of towers create conditions for essential changes of specific pictures of the palace complex with the movement of the viewer: one tower grows behind others, large walls and sites with apertures, porches, and galleries alternate. *Structures uniting active perceptive elements:* there are recurrences of the outlines of towers, the general corners of slopes of roofs, recurrences of ratios of sides of rectangular elements.

Figure 3. *Palace in Kolomenskoe: a. southeast façade, b. northeast façade. Structures of semantic relations of the material space, expressed by perception: three levels of inhabited mansion designate three worlds of human existence in the theological traditions of the Russian architecture of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries by Maxim Grek (Brunov 1988: 197). Structures of visual sign systems: relations of heights of the main mansional towers express the importance of members of imperial family, ball-shaped roof with the State Emblem above — autocracy, the State Emblem with double eagle — a mansion of the Tsar; metric and rhythmic structures of basic elements — towers, sites of walls, roofs, embrasures, elements of different materials and colors; relations of the rising and falling of a silhouette, distinction of smooth surfaces smooth, punctured by embrasures and finely dismembered.*

Figure 4. *Temple of the Holy Mother's Cover (Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral) in Moscow (1555–1561). Architects are Barma and Postnik*

Language type systems become the material for the formation of semi-otic systems, which are 'overbuilt' above, organize their own sign formations, and become involved in concrete processes of activity, communication, and noesis.

Figure 5. *Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral. Structures of the plan elements: proportions in geometrical similarity*

Semiotic systems of mental activities (18) work as communication tools because of their modelling capacity. They develop on the basis of different types of activities and models.

In this aspect, the differences among vital-communicative, business, and art semiotic systems are the most apparent (Somov 2001). Common vital-communicative information includes uncertainties, hints, and metaphors, i.e., it is based on the use of connotative codes (Danesi 1999). Business information must be precise and does not allow any connotations. Art information (like business) develops from a common source, but tends to uncertainties, connotations, and diffused meanings; often, it has no correspondence with definite objects and situations. Some types and directions of art illustrate this visually, e.g., symphonic music or abstract painting. The development of these principally different semiotic systems and corresponding types of information is based on the domination of different sign types (III and IV) and models I and II. In their turn, they depend on differences in activities and mental activities.

At the level of signs and models, there are differences among signs that are oriented towards the reflection of structures or symptoms and

Figure 6. *Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral. Structures of the plan elements: proportions in geometrical similarity*

appellations in models I and II, respectively. Scheme, sketch, formal instruction, and business telegrams correspond to reality I, while expressive picture or billet-doux correspond to reality II. Emotions accompanying symptoms and appellations can be regarded as varieties of orientation meanings (Lemke 1983, 1988). At the same time, in life and scientific communication, the information included in symbols by Bühler (1978 [1934]) usually must be separated from motivation and emotions. In art, this information is additional and rather completes emotional meanings, which are related to fundamental needs and corresponding feelings: compassion, love, hate, or kindness.

The processes where reality I prevails are characterized by the necessity of efficiently regulating objects and acts in collective actions. In connection with this, specific communication systems develop. A typical feature of such systems is the absence of significant connotativity. It is explained by the belonging of this communication to activity with precise changes and models of situations, while the high connotativity of art is related to the uncertainty of its participation in any activity and situations. Note

Figure 7. *Temple of the Holy Mother's Cover (Vasily Blazhenny Cathedral). Structures in the organization of the basic perceptive elements of the cathedral: geometrical recurrences of triangles and inclinations*

Figure 8. *Temple of the Holy Mother's Cover (Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral). Configuration organizing silhouettes of cathedral heads: the general configuration organizes perceptual elements (signals). It is also a latent sign (connotation), designating the uniform large head. The Cross is also latent in the outlines of heads and the common composition. According to sixteenth century representations 'Cross Vivifying' was not only a sign but it also had the property of extrasensory healing influence (Brunov 1988: 150)*

that, in the case of the politicization of art and its submission to sociopolitical programs and goals, new requirements to semiotic systems appear, e.g., availability to public, demonstrativeness, correspondence to political mythology, etc. In a most apparent way, this was demonstrated in the art of totalitarian regimes of the twentieth century. From the viewpoint of connotativity and relation with activities, common vital systems of communication occupy an intermediate position between business and art

Figure 9. *Temple of the Holy Mother's Cover (Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral). Structures organizing silhouettes of cathedral heads. Organizing structures — proportions — strengthen the connotation of cathedral head*

semiotic systems. The discussion of business demands the usage of a 'language of definiteness.' At the same time, vital communications are often irrational. This feature is explained by the situations and models II. A significant part of human communication is represented by sympathies, antipathies, compassions, self-affirmations, and other demonstrations of fundamental meanings and corresponding intentions. This is supported by the most widespread type of communication — a useless chitchat where the discussed objects are either only a cause for spiritual contacts of persons or serve to demonstrate the ambitions of communicating persons.

Figure 10. *Temple of the Holy Mother's Cover (Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral). Structures organizing silhouettes: common proportions of rectangulars of cathedral heads. At the same time, organizing structures and forms carry out semantic functions*

In other dimension, different semiotic systems develop in noesis. Evolving from mental activity, noesis develops its own tools, which often differ from the communicative ones. The languages of philosophy and particular sciences are not used in business communication; as well, the languages of elite art do not favor social communication in a society. Both of them have, first and foremost, cognitive functions.

Despite the differences in sign instruments of modelling, models I and II can be interrelated. Emotional interrelations among people are related to their estate and business relations; the perception of art combines

Figure 11. *Temple of the Holy Mother's Cover (Vasily Blazhenniy Cathedral). Structures organizing active perceptual elements (signals) and strengthening signs — cathedral heads and towers: proportions of basic elements — geometrical elements. Due to geometrical similarities uniform visual – sign integrity of architectural product is formed. Geometrical similarities in works of antiquity and the Renaissance were analyzed by August Tirsch at the beginning of the twentieth century. Researchers of architecture considered these touches mainly as tradition. However, with the semiotics approach to proportions as a types of organizing structure, the more fundamental role of composite means of such a type is evinced*

penetrations into fancies with understanding of the structure of social relations. In addition, high connotativity of sign systems does not mean that they cannot carry clear messages and texts. On the contrary, the combination of systems of different connotations can produce more stable semantic systems and texts. This is why the explorers find the hypertexts

Figure 12. *Pashkov's house in Moscow (1784–1786). Architect is Vasily I. Bazhenov*

Figure 13. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. The basic structures and elements of visual sign systemity. Geometrical similarities*

containing the models of man and society in magnum opuses. In this case, imaginative cognition includes the elements of scientific cognition, as it is based on the simulation of relations and structures of life situations, heroes, and social phenomena. At the same time, both the instruments and results of imaginative cognition differ from scientific cognition. First, this is explained by the differences in operations: operations with multisign images and forms is typical for art, while relations, structures, and precise characteristics are inherent to science. It is quicker to invent something convincing using images and forms than to understand relations and structures. This is why science fiction usually precedes scientific theories and forecasts, and imaginative cognition in general precedes scientific cognition.

Figure 14. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Traditional church — the sign form organizing the building. The structures forming a sign of tradition, mainly, of a proportion of elements. The role of structures in the formation of architectural semantics is evident*

Figure 15. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Groups of active perceptive elements and relations. Organizing structures: topological recurrences and binary groups of elements*

Figure 16. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Groups of active perceptive elements and relations. Organizing structures: triads*

The reality of vital processes is ramified. It unites different types of activity and different cycle processes of communication and noesis, which are blocked with the processes and motivations of orientation and evaluation. In this case, multilateral semiotic systems prove to be the most efficient. They unite semiotic systems of separate types and correspond in general to 'fundamental meanings,' needs, and related intentions. These semiotic systems are represented, first, by religious, ideological, and political doctrines, partly involving art. In these multilateral systems, certain specific systems and mechanisms of information and direction are especially important (taboos, moral rules, and the deeds of heroes). The study of these phenomena as components of semiotic systems envisages the interrelations between the realities I and II or III and IV.

Figure 17. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Groups of active perceptible elements and relations. Organizing structures: active pieces of lines*

Figure 18. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Groups of active perceptible elements and relations. Organizing structures: recurrences of elements with triads of apertures*

The dependence of systems on activity leads to the formation of stable system-structural formations, which can function in a relatively independent way. In systemology, this corresponds to the term 'fragmentation systems' (Mel'nikov 1982). These formations can migrate within a socium and become interiorized in the human psychic world.

System-structural formations of a fragmentation type (19) develop on the basis of structures and signs. These formations are implemented in behavior and activity as they are, without any transformations of their structures. Various tropes and stamps are formed seeming to repeat instincts in a social domain and replace mental activity. These are stereotypes of behavior, trade skills, standard designs, economy traditions, etiquette rules, rites, political slogans, and forms of art technologies and myths.

Figure 19. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Groups of active perceptive elements and relations. Organizing structures: recurrence of elements with five apertures*

Fragmentation formations can be represented by system-structural formations of realities I and II. The type of an apartment building with blocked sections has a pure economic and technological basis. The type of a temple is a sign formation with a very complicated semantic system-ity and mythological basis. At the same time, there are numerous architectural constructions uniting systems I and II, which have an equally vital importance. This can be illustrated by various prototypes of houses of folk architecture: atrium houses of the Mediterranean region, clannish towers of the Near and Middle East, blocked houses of artisans and traders of Mediaeval Europe, houses and homesteads of Russian towns, and different derivatives and variations of these prototypes in the history of architecture. Such prototypes synthesize the systems of husbandry organization and the vital processes of genera and families, defense from enemies and robbers, refuge from climatic effect, building, and construction, together with communicative-sign systems of religions, ethnoses, and territories. Something similar to the functioning of architectural prototypes can be found in other spheres of life where the formations of the types I, II, and I–II are noticeable (18).

These formations have specific functions at different levels. In reality I, they deliberate people from the tension of inventive mental activity; in reality II, they make it possible to exclude the emotional component from communicative processes by creating a semiotic layer of automatic evaluations, communications, and deeds. The formations of fragmentation type can be born by fundamental intentions, vital processes, and ideological and sociopolitical programs; they may represent petrified connotations, enormous simulacra, forms, etc. It is important that migrations, formation, and development of fragmentation constructions occur both

Figure 20. *Pashkov's house in Moscow. Groups of active perceptive elements and relations. Organizing structures: geometrical similarities of the central part of the building*

in the ontogenesis and phylogenesis of humans, forming a concrete and quasi-fixed surface crust over a general volcanic movement of semiotic systems of mental activity. This is why multiple empirical studies of fragmentation constructions are efficient for the formation of theoretical semiotics.

The organization of all models and signs is determined by certain principles.

The principles of sign organization III reflecting the organization of reality I (20) differ from those of internal regulation or *sign organization corresponding to reality II* (21). The differences became apparent in two well-known phenomena. First principles are expressed via a tough and practical mind, while those of the second type, via irrational human intentions and elements or spiritual contacts.

Principles I–III (20) organize objects in accordance with given characteristics, changes in material objects, and domination of corresponding motives and goals. Various principles of this type are known as optimality, efficiency, practical effect, expanded production, capital accumulation, sustainable development of social systems, etc. These principles are interrelated; however, this domain is far out of the domain of semiotics. It is significant that sign systems III are formed in accordance with this group of principles. In systems III, the changes in reality I are simulated and the selectivity of interrelations and situation structures within sign systems of models of reality I is manifested.

Principles IV (21) are of another nature. The cogency and effect of ideas or images are very far from those of calculations made by managers and engineers. This difference results from the fact that the organization involves signs (IV), including the processes of self-organization of sign systems, rather than changes in material objects and behavior. The processes of self-organization (3, 4) and internal reflections are projected primarily to situations II.

The processes of sign organization follow a *common principle* (22b), which was described by Peirce as a general naturalistic principle and is known as ‘distrust — faith.’ Peirce wrote that the words ‘distrust’ and ‘faith’ are usually used in religious and other serious discussions. However, he stressed that he used them for each problem, independently of whether it is small or large and illustrated this by the decision of paying for train or horse transport, depending on the available sum of money. The next illustration was the perception of music with a guessable melody (Peirce 1878). Comparing this principle with modern ideas of information structure and different principles of psychology, aesthetics, and information theory, it is possible to say that the signs have a trend towards being convictive. Internal cogency represented as the movement from distrust to faith is materialized and sustained by structural organization and definiteness of interrelations of sign representamens, corresponding designates, or intentions.

Philosophers tried to digest Peirce’s principle from the viewpoint of interaction among global spiritual phenomena and cognizability of the

world. However, many 'local' phenomena (formation of visual image, clear sense, precise information, convictive idea, and available form) are also explained by this general principle. For semiotics, it is important that signs 'tend to become' organized. This is fixed in the particular principles of psychology, aesthetics, theories of arts, and applied theories of information (principles of wholeness, pregnancy, expression of the main idea, unity and plurality of values, signature of messages, unity of sense material, definiteness of difference or equity, etc.). This diversity indicates that the general semiotic principle (22b) is incarnated in all aspects, systems, and mechanisms, at all levels of developing semiotic systems. It appears in the most complete way in sign-synthesizing architectural forms where the systems are formed in three semiotic aspects: pragmatics, semantics, and syntactics (Somov 2001). These implementations of semiotic principle become most apparent in styles and directions of art. Style formation detects dominating intentions, maintained vital processes, communicative situations, ideological program of personal and social life and development (pragmatics). It reveals semantic dominants: pathos, basic connotations of an epoch, and central 'concepts forming semantic rules' (Morris 1971: 22–23) (semantics). Typical distinctions, structures, and elements are formed, including those loaned from other styles and cultures together with realities and semantic systems (syntactics). Something similar occurs during the formation of psychic world of a human in general. The need in an internal structural organization of signs generates different systems, mechanisms, and levels, as well as the general organization of this psychic world with inherent intentions. This is why, unlike the void of 'objective reality,' this world is full of life of signs (Sebeok 1999). 'Real life is always nothing but a dream,' said one of Fellini's heroes; this is the best illustration of the essence of naturalistic understanding of organization of sign systems. The contradictions in the implementation of principles 20 and 21 become apparent in basic contradictions of a personality and society, spiritual world and culture, and opposition of some cultures and ideologies. These contradictions are the most pronounced in a person's psyche when practical considerations conflict with feelings and spiritual intentions or a business goal contradicts psychological comfort. These contradictions are visual in the objects of the artificial environment, which are available for studies. A module helping to simplify technological processes creates repeating standard elements in dwelling complexes, which are very unfavorable for the information, coding of signs, and connotations. At the same time, rhythm based on other relations, such as diversity and order of apertures and contrasts of texture of wall areas or the color of wall surfaces, makes it possible to alter the utilitarian structure by forming a layer of structures and diversity of information (Somov

2002). Utilitarianism and elementary technology are opposed to intentional information, first, due to incomplete materialization of structures. These contradictions can be eliminated by synthesizing abstract structures I and II.

The unity of realities I and II, III and IV is manifested in mutual transitions of large semiotic structures. Expedience appears as beauty, economical effectiveness, social benefit (transitions from I and III to II and IV). Beauty helps to evaluate rational decisions, advanced social ideals enhance the rationalization of production and social relations (II and IV → III and I). Unity, mutual transitions, and the principal possibility of harmony among various realities can be explained by the unity of their structures and effect of a *general principle of structural organization* (22a), which is in this or that way examined in different philosophical and systemological concepts.

It is quite evident that, from the viewpoint of this suggested model, there are no deep differences among empirical objects of semiotic studies: personality, society, and culture. This continues the traditional ideas of interiorization of social phenomena in human psychic world, materialization of human nature in a socium, and interrelations and reproductions of these mechanisms in culture. This seems to be the manifestation of methodological effectiveness of the model discussed, which makes it possible to develop theoretical anthroposemiotics using a large basis of an empirical knowledge of humanitarian sciences.

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